

PHOTOGRAPH FROM UNITED PRESS INTERNATIONAL

Dr. Pauling receiving the Nobel Prize.

That Man... Pauling!

The new book by Linus Pauling (Vitamin C and the Common Cold, W. H. Freeman and Co., San Francisco, 1970, 122 pages, \$3.95; paperback, \$1.95) has caused a stir in the field of nutrition. Three authorities—a renowned clinician, Russel V. Lee; a famous nutritionist, Fredrick J. Stare; and a gifted author of texts in medicine and nutrition, Reginald Passmore—were asked to prepare reviews of this controversial book. The editor has also written a review. None of the four reviewers knew what the others had written when his contribution was composed.

Shaking Up The Doctors

by Russel V. Lee, M.D., Emeritus Professor of Medicine, Stanford University, Consultant, Palo Alto Clinic, Palo Alto, California.

Any pronouncement by a person of such prestige as Linus Pauling must be given the most serious consideration. But in *Wisdom of the West*, Bertrand Russell pointed out fallacies in the reasoning of the giants, Socrates, Plato, and Aristotle, while at the same time acknowledging the immense debt philosophy owed to them. Linus Pauling, two-time Nobel Prize winner, is not sacrosanct, and certainly such sweeping statements as he makes in this book require critical appraisal.

But one must grant that in making his points he has followed proper scientific guidelines—review of the literature, formulation of an hypothesis (i.e., very large doses of ascorbic acid produce effects far more extensive than merely the prevention of scurvy), experiments (on himself) to validate the non-toxicity of these large doses, and conclusions

based on these data. The conclusions are that doses of ascorbic acid far greater than have previously been used, actually up to ten grams a day, are harmless and probably greatly reduce the incidence of viral colds. The suggestion that the mode of action is the synthesis of interferon which probably prevents the entrance of the virus into the cell is new and deserves careful experimental verification. There are two points made by Dr. Pauling for which he deserves a big plus: One is his warning against unjustified restrictions imposed arbitrarily by the FDA on the use of vitamins and statements about them. The other is an exposure of the almost fraudulent markup (12,000 times, in one instance) in the price of such products. He supplements this with clear advice as to what to buy, and in what form and for what

price. This should be done for many over-the-counter remedies. His notes on the harmful effects of the commonly used cold remedies are also very well taken, and will be most influential in the marketplace.

The book, as one would expect, is well-written, well-documented, fills a fervent longing (how to cure a cold),

and is having a tremendous sale. Its effect will be great. But what are obviously needed are well-controlled, large-scale experiments to verify his statements or to refute them. I have already suggested that the Stanford Student Health Service conduct such a study. There should be 5,000 students involved, 2,500 on ascorbic acid and

2,500 for controls; the study should go over a three-year period. Dr. Pauling makes a sufficient case to justify such an experiment and the stakes—in terms of money, three to fifteen billion dollars—as he points out, are surely great enough to justify such an experiment. More books like this would shake up doctors, as they should be shaken.

New Nostrum

by Reginald Passmore, M. D.
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Dr. Passmore (with Dr. S. Davidson)
is author of the book, *Human Nutrition*
and *Dietetics*, The Williams &
Wilkins Co., Baltimore (1966).

Just over sixty years ago, the world-famous Russian zoologist, Elie Metchnikoff, persuaded large numbers of fashionable people in Europe and America to drink sour milk daily with the aim of establishing *Lactobacillus bulgaricus* in their colons, and thereby prolong life. Metchnikoff's scientific discoveries are still remembered and discussed and many of us continue to drink and enjoy yoghurt, but the role of the Bulgarian bacillus as an elixir of life has been forgotten. Now the best-known internationally of all America's famous scientists has put forward a new elixir. Linus Pauling describes how his book began: "In April 1966 I received a letter from Dr. Irwin Stone. He mentioned that I had expressed a desire to live for the next fifteen or twenty years. He said that he would like to see me in

good health for the next fifty years, and that he was accordingly sending me a description of his high-level ascorbic acid regimen which he had developed during the preceding three decades. My wife and I began the regimen recommended by Dr. Stone. We noticed an increased feeling of well-being, and especially a striking decrease in the number of colds that we caught, and in their severity."

The regimen that Pauling recommends for "good health for many people" is the ingestion of one to two grams of ascorbic acid daily (1,000 mg to 2,000 mg). "Some may require less and others up to 5,000 mg per day." At the first sign of a cold, he recommends, "Begin the treatment by swallowing one or two 500 mg tablets. Continue the treatment for several hours by taking an additional tablet or two tablets every hour."

Just how unorthodox this view is may be seen by comparing it with the recommended dietary allowance of 60 mg per day made by the Food and Nutrition Board of the National Research Council. This recommendation itself is considered to be needlessly large in Britain, where the recommended intake is 30 mg per day. Pauling is well aware of the medical profession's orthodox view of the relation of ascorbic acid to the common cold, which he aptly sums up in a quotation from Dr. F. J. Stare: "There is no conclusive evidence that ascorbic acid has any protective effect against, or any therapeutic effect on the course of the common cold in healthy people, not depleted of ascorbic acid. There is also no evidence for a general antiviral or symptomatic prophylactic effect of ascorbic acid."

Pauling has read widely in the literature of ascorbic acid and of the common cold. Most of this book is first-class popular scientific writing. The chapters on the "Common Cold,"

"Scurvy," "The Discovery of Vitamins," "Orthomolecular Medicine," and "Biochemical Individuality," which together make up a large part of the book, are each admirable vignettes, and present the reader with facets of both history and modern ideas in biochemistry and medicine. They are far from heretical, but are irrelevant to his main thesis.

The chapter on ascorbic acid and the common cold reviews the literature on the clinical trials of ascorbic acid critically and accurately, as far as I have checked. At least ten prophylactic trials have been reported using daily doses of, usually, 100 to 200 mg. The two largest of these trials (each involving over 1,000 subjects and lasting many months) were carried out in Minneapolis in 1939-40, and in Edinburgh in 1940-41. It is mainly on those two that the orthodox view already quoted rests. Pauling points out that in both these trials the number and the severity of the colds were slightly less in the group receiving ascorbic acid than in the group receiving placebo pills. He also points out minor ways in which, in each trial, the treated and untreated groups were not quite compatible. I have reread the original accounts of these trials carefully. Pauling's comments, while factual and accurate, seem in no way to invalidate the original interpretation of both trials by their authors, which was that the ascorbic acid had no practical effect. In any case, this point is really not relevant, as at best only a small number of persons could have benefited from the relatively small doses given. Pauling's claim is for large doses.

The claim appears to rest on the subjective impressions of Dr. Pauling, Mrs. Pauling, Dr. Irwin Stone, Dr. Szent-Gyorgyi and others who feel well and say that they have few colds when taking one gram or more of ascorbic acid daily. Pauling also quotes the

clinical impressions and writings of Dr. Edmie Regnier of Salem, Massachusetts, and Dr. Gildersleeve; but these authors write in journals of little international repute, which are not available for checking in Edinburgh libraries. Dr. Ritzel, a Swiss physician, has, however, reported some freedom from respiratory infection in skiers given 1,000 mg of ascorbic acid daily. This work seems well done, but there were only 279 persons in his trial.

Because Pauling's claim is not supported by evidence does not infer that it is wrong, but there are two reasons that suggest to me that it is unlikely to be right: There is no epidemiological support. If ascorbic acid intake and the common cold were in any way related, one would expect a high incidence of colds where intakes were low. The American recommended allowance of 60 mg per day and the British one of 30 mg per day probably reflect national eating habits; in India and Pakistan, most people would have intakes of 15 mg per day or less. I know of no records, but it is my impression that Americans have more numerous and severe colds at home than do the British, Indians, or Pakistanis. Although the viruses responsible for upper respiratory infections are widespread in India and Pakistan and infections occur readily, they do not appear unduly common—despite the low intakes of the vitamin.

Secondly, Pauling's claim is not supported by any theoretical concept of how the vitamin might work at the molecular level. Protection could be by strengthening the membrane barrier of the epithelial cells which the viruses must cross to enter the cells, by

direct attack on the viruses in the cells, and by strengthening the cellular or humoral immune defenses of the body. Pauling's excellent little chapter on orthomolecular medicine has no mention of vitamin C or the common cold.

The claim is, however, supported by a theoretical argument from evolution, which is certainly ingenious. Pauling points out that ascorbic acid, unlike the other water-soluble vitamins, thiamine, riboflavin, and niacin, is not an essential dietary factor for most mammals, which still retain the ability to synthesize it. The ability to synthesize vitamins, it is postulated, is lost in evolution when the normal diet provides a sufficiency. The unneeded synthetic enzymic apparatus then complicates cells unnecessarily, as it is selected against in the evolutionary process. The ability of most mammals to synthesize ascorbic acid indicates, it is postulated, that their needs for this vitamin exceed the amounts often provided in their diets. Pauling then carries out an arithmetical exercise. He takes the analytical figures for 110 raw natural plant foods and calculates the content of water-soluble vitamins present in an amount providing 2,500 kcal. He divides these figures by the recommended daily allowance for an adult. The average ratios of plant food content to recommended allowance are 3.8, 3.6, and 2.5 respectively for thiamine, riboflavin, and niacin, but of a different order, 42, for ascorbic acid. The average ascorbic acid content of the fourteen plant foods richest in vitamin C provide 9.4 gm per 2,500 kcal. This figure is taken as the upper limit for the optimum daily intake for many.

It is concluded that optimum daily intakes lie between 2.3 and 9 gm. This is a fascinating new approach to recommended allowances, but it hardly makes sense. How would carnivorous man survive, if his daily intake of this important vitamin was four orders of magnitude away from the optimum?

Such is Pauling's reputation that no doubt millions of people both in America and Europe will dose themselves with vitamin C in the coming years. I guess that all this effort will not prevent a single cold or add a year to life, but like Metchnikoff's sour milk it will do no bodily harm and may have indirect benefit, especially to the supplier's pocket. Ascorbic acid is cheap, and Pauling goes to pains to tell his readers how to shop for it and to avoid paying inflated prices. He also states that U.S. citizens spend \$500,000,000 a year on cold medicines; he comments rightly that none of these prevent colds and some are toxic. Most of us need a nostrum on occasions, and ascorbic acid powder serves as a cheap and harmless one. Personally I prefer to take my vitamin C in the form of fruit juice, and am satisfied that one glass—besides being pleasant—meets my vitamin needs for the day. We know next to nothing about how to prevent or treat a cold. And I agree with Pauling that it is an important scientific problem with immense economic consequences. Meanwhile, in our present state of ignorance, my tip when you feel a cold coming on is to go home, take a Scotch—with none of that awful water and ice which spoil the taste—and go to bed. This is a real comfort. It is also a social duty as it minimizes the chance of infecting others.

Not Quite Cricket

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Dr. Pauling's nutritional comments of recent times have disappointed us, not only because they make no sense in terms of modern medicine or nutrition, but also in the irresponsible way they arouse false hopes in those who have diseases which Pauling feels can be successfully treated by his "vitamin therapy." Two examples: first, his comments on the importance of various vitamins in the treatment and prevention of "mental disease," particularly schizophrenia (*Science* 160: 265, 1968); second, his more recent comments to the press about large amounts of vitamin C leading "... to improvement in general health and to increased resist-

ance to infectious diseases including the common cold."

Pauling's views on vitamin C are briefly stated in this book published early last December and well publicized a few weeks prior to publication. As a result, many pharmacies were out of vitamin C, the bookstores are out of the book, and the \$3.95 for the book would buy quite a bit of vitamin C or facial tissues for drippy noses.

FJS seems to be the villain in Pauling's book, as exemplified by his comments on pages 2, 3, 40, and 51. These unkind comments are not quite "cricket" for a man of Pauling's stature. Actually, Pauling wrote FJS on December 10, 1969, inquiring about an "off-the-cuff" remark (actually made over the telephone) to a magazine writer and which eventually wound up in a "quote" in the November, 1969 issue of a magazine, *Mademoiselle*. FJS had referred to a study done some 30 years ago at the University of Minnesota, and which, as he recalled, involved some 5,000 students. Half were given large amounts of vitamin C, half placebos, and no difference was found in the frequency or severity of colds. Pauling wrote, "... for some reason I have not run across this work," and he asked if FJS would send him this reference and references to any similar studies.

Obviously, one would not reply to Pauling with an "off-the-cuff" letter trying to remember what he had read some 30 years ago. Hence, a trip to the library and then a reply on December 22, 1969: "The statement about studies of the common cold involving 5,000 students . . . is a little mixed-up but not appreciably so. . . In these studies 12 to 15 so-called 'cold remedies' were studied, with appropriate placebos, and somewhat more than 5,000 students were involved in the total study. However, those . . . involved in the use of various vitamin preparations were . . . of the order of 250 with a control group approximating 200. The largest experimental group was given vitamin C at a dosage of 200 mg per day during the 'cold season,' a period of about six months."

This letter provided Professor Pauling with the two references to these studies plus three other specific references. The letter ended: "I hope I have answered the various questions in your letter of December 10 to your satisfaction. Please let me know at any time if you have other questions on nutrition that you think I or any of my associates

could be helpful in answering."

On January 26, 1970, Pauling replied: "I am glad to have the references given in your letter."

In view of this correspondence it seems a little odd that Pauling wrote about FJS in his book as he did, particularly the footnote on page 40, stating that FJS had reported this study "rather inaccurately."

Pauling's book does not contain acceptable scientific evidence with appropriate controls to support his testimonials, or those of others, that vitamin C will actually deter or mitigate the common cold. Most scientists knowledgeable in vitamin C and its metabolism know that in amounts of more than 25 to 30 mg per day vitamin C is readily excreted in the urine, and much more of it is excreted as the intake is increased. Toxicity is not apparent in adults in reasonably large doses, but when one gets to Pauling's recommendation of 10 to 15 grams per day (page 86)—huge doses—we are not so sure. Anything can be toxic if a sufficient amount is taken. Actually, a report in the Russian medical literature (Biull, Eksp, *Biol. Med.* 8: 96, 1966) mentions that 6 grams of ascorbic acid per day for 3 successive days has been used to abort women with apparent success in 16 of 20 women.

Actually, Pauling states (page 5) "I do not know how effective this regimen really is." If that is the case, what is the point of raising false hopes in the many millions who have colds until he or others find out if it is effective?

It is questionable whether increasing the intake of vitamin C results in correspondingly higher blood concentrations over the wide range that Pauling claims. A recent Japanese study (*Shikoku Acta Med.* 22:382, 1966) showed that sustained blood concentrations did not exceed 1.39 mg%. And this maximum level was reached with doses of only 90-100 mg per day after seven to eight weeks. Furthermore, study of ¹⁴C-labeled ascorbic acid in man has resulted in the conclusion that the maximum quantity that can be metabolized by adult man is only 40 mg/day (*Am. J. Clin. Nutr.* 20:583, 1967). Thus, an oral intake of 200 mg used in many previous "cold studies" would appear to be more than adequate for any physiological requirements man might have. Until these scientifically acceptable pieces of data are refuted by the usual scientific methods, one cannot support speculation to the contrary. It seems

unwise to us for Pauling to recommend multivitamin supplements (pages 93-97) after a general discussion which urges the reader to take essentially unlimited amounts of a specific vitamin. This is likely to result in the impression that other vitamins may be beneficial in huge amounts. With children, this could be dangerous, especially with vitamins A and D.

As in any good salesmanship, a strong bias pervades the writing of this book to make it sound convincing to the nutritionally uninformed. The careful reader who nears the end of the book will learn of a study which contradicts the general conclusions of the author. An English study is described using carefully controlled methods, including actual virus inoculations and administration of 3 grams of vitamin C per day. The results showed no difference between control and treatment groups, so the data are relegated to the third appendix, page 101. Incidentally, this is one of the references sent Pauling in the letter of December 22, 1969.

Acceptable scientific tests of proof of the efficacy of ascorbic acid in the prevention or treatment of the common cold are not available to date. Notwithstanding the apparent safety accorded to ascorbic acid, the wide variation in biological responses (referred to in chapter 8) and the large number of people who may be exposed to Pauling's large dosages will probably unveil a percentage of unsuspecting persons who may suffer as-yet-unknown damage—a possibility that should not be taken lightly by men of science. For example, it has been well-known for many years that vitamin C increases the absorption of iron. Does the same happen with other minerals, including one currently in the news—mercury? If so, the vitamin C cultists may be in for some trouble far more serious than a drippy nose!

Vitamin C and the Common Cold is the second nutritional fairy tale (the first was "Orthomolecular Psychiatry," *Science* 160: 265, 1968) to come from this very intelligent and likable man. Like Hansel and Gretel, he is lost in the woods—of health and nutrition, areas outside his competence.

We note that the book is dedicated to Albert Szent-Gyorgyi "who discovered ascorbic acid." It would have been more accurate, and certainly considerate, to dedicate it to Szent-Gyorgyi and Charles Glen King, co-discoverers of this vitamin.